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List of abbreviations

AFM	Atomic Force Microscope
AFQ	Accelerated Fuel Qualification
CERCER	Ceramic-in-Ceramic
CERMET	Ceramic-in-Metal
DBA	Design Beyond Accident
EGIF	Expert Group on Innovative Fuels
FPC	Fuel Performance Code
GFR	Gas-cooled Fast Reactor
HTGR	High-temperature Gas-cooled Reactor
LOCA	Loss of Coolant Accident
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MA	Minor Actinide
MOX	Mixed Oxide
MSR	Molten Salt Reactor
NEA	Nuclear Energy Agency
PIE	Post Irradiation Examination
PHWR	Pressurized Heavy Water Reactor
SCWR	Super-Critical Water Reactor
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SFR	Sodium Fast Reactor
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscope
TRISO	TRi-structural ISOtropic
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
URS	User Requirement Specification
VHTR	Very High Temperature Reactor

Summary

This document is a report written for the subtask “6.4.3 Overview of testing procedures for the characterization of innovative fuels” which is the part of the pre-selected project “6.4 Preliminary analysis of the requirements for selected test-beds for nuclear materials” related to the Work Package 6 of the CONNECT-NM Partnership.

The report summarises the development of innovative fuels based on the Technical Readiness Level (TRL). It is further combined with the nuclear material identity published by ORIENT-NM. The report additionally provides information on the fuel qualification process either via the classical or accelerated approaches including the utilisation of the Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT), the general required properties of innovative fuels including the pre- and post-irradiation examinations (PIEs) and some practical examples.

The PIRT itself can be seen as an important step gap assessment of the fuel material properties as it assesses not only the importance of each necessary aspect or scenario needed for fuel qualification but also the knowledge availability.

The practical examples summarised in this report will hopefully provide information on the necessary fuel properties and parameters for the qualification process. It is important to note that the examples are simply proposals in which they need to be adjusted based on the specific fuel and technology.

The report is structured in accordance with the Work Package Work Plan outlined in the Annex I to the CONNECT-NM Grant Agreement.

1. Introduction

This document is an internal “Deliverable 6.4.4 - URS Pre- and PIE on Innovative Fuel” which is the part of the pre-selected project “6.4 Preliminary analysis of the requirements for selected test-beds for nuclear materials” related to the Work Package 6 of the CONNECT-NM Partnership.

This first chapter of the current document serves an introduction to highlight the development of the fuel qualification around the world in the last and current years. The whole document has the objective to provide a general guideline or user requirement for the pre- and post irradiation examination as part of the fuel qualification program.

The guideline itself is not binding and is solely summarized as an informative guideline. Several modifications on the guideline may be required depending on the purpose and the specific requirement of the Nuclear Safety Agency of each specific country. Several practical examples will additionally be proposed.

Additionally, this document is completed with some general required properties of nuclear fuel and summary of available labs to perform the Pre- and PIE. The practical examples of pre- and PIE of MOX and U-Zr metallic fuels are added.

2. Innovative Fuels

The development of nuclear fuels around the world has been going on for such a long time, even before the first installation of the nuclear power plant. These developments are carried out in order to increase the safety and provide better performance fuel leading to safer and more efficient nuclear power plant. Furthermore, with the current needs to have more reliable energy production, the development and improvement of the nuclear fuel become more imminent.

In 2014, the NEA Expert Group on Innovative Fuel Elements (EGIFE) published a report on the “State-of-the-art Report on Innovative Fuels for Advanced Nuclear Systems” covering several fuel types which contains minor actinides [1]:

- metallic fuels,
- oxide fuels,
- nitride fuels,
- dispersion fuels (including ceramic-in-ceramic (CERCER) and ceramic-in-metal (CERMET) dispersions), and
- special mechanical fuel forms (particle fuels, sphere-pac, vibro-pac).

The NEA EGIFE merely included minor actinide as innovative fuels, however, it is important to note that Accident Tolerance Fuel (ATF) for Gen-III (e.g. U_2Si_3 , UO_2 with additives Cr_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , etc., and U-Mo alloy) and fuels for Gen-IV (TRISO, metallic fuels U-Zr, U-Pu-Zr, U-Mo, etc., molten salt and nitride fuels) can also be categorised as innovative fuels.

2.1 Technical Readiness Level (TRL)

Similar to other technologies, nuclear fuels are developed following thorough sequences activities and processes. Technical readiness level (TRL), see the definition of each TRL level in Table 1, is used to measure and quantify the progress in which two elements, further combined to define a final TRL level, are generally used to evaluate the maturity level of a new fuel in term of readiness and deployment [2]:

- Fabrication Process Maturity: to measure how well the fabrication process is understood and validated.
- Fuel Performance Maturity: to measure how well the in-pile performance of the fuel is understood and validated.

The TRL includes not only pre-IE and PIE but also irradiation. In 2018, Shepherd, et al. summarized the technical Readiness Level (TRLs) of several innovative fuels (including a mentioned on liquid metal) (Table 2) [3]. Several fuels, such as MA, Zr-hydride based, U_2Si_3 , and molten salt fuels are still in the Proof-of-principle phase, TRL level 4 -5.

Table 1 Typical TRL definition for fuels, summarised from Shepherd, D. J., et al. [3] and Carmack, et. al. [2].

1	Proof-of-concept	A new concept is proposed. Research identifies the basic principles that underlie the technology e.g. promising materials and/or geometry have been identified.
2		Technical options are ranked. Practical applications suggested and concepts formulated e.g. fuel, cladding and/or fuel assembly designs have been established.
3		Basic components fabricated and successfully demonstrated. e.g. fuel and/or cladding components have been manufactured and tested out-of-reactor and/or irradiated as a component only.
4	Proof-of-principle	Integration of components into a basic system e.g. representative assembly sections have been manufactured and subjected to out-of-reactor tests and/or test reactor irradiation trials of individual rods have been conducted with only limited success
5		Basic system successfully demonstrated e.g. test rods have been irradiated and performed successfully in a test reactor (demonstrated by in-reactor instrumentation and/or post-irradiation examination (PIE) and/or post-irradiation mechanical testing).
6		Prototype construction (much more representative than the basic system) e.g. lead use assemblies have been fabricated, and potentially irradiated in a prototype or commercial reactor but with only limited success
7	Proof-of-performance	Prototype successfully demonstrated e.g. lead use assemblies have performed successfully in a prototype or commercial reactor (demonstrated by PIE and/or in-core monitoring)
8		Actual system constructed and commissioned e.g. assemblies fabricated in reload quantities; may include irradiation with only limited success
9		Successful operation of actual system e.g. assemblies have performed successfully under irradiation in reload quantities (demonstrated by surveillance programme) 8 Actual system constructed and commissioned.

Table 2 Examples of the innovative fuels including their best case TRL [3].

Fuel categories		Best case TRL	Remarks
Oxide Fuel	MOX (<12% PuO ₂)	9*	Used in many commercial LWRs [4].
	Advanced MOX	9	High PuO ₂ content MOX used in commercial scale SFR in Russia [4].
	Advanced UO ₂	9	Commercially produced by AREVA (Cr ₂ O ₃) and Westinghouse (Cr ₂ O ₃ -Al ₂ O ₃) [4].
	ThO ₂	8	A significant amount of thorium bearing fuels has been irradiated in commercial PHWRs in India [5].
	Minor Actinide transmutation fuels/targets(MAs)	4	A number of test irradiations of MA fuels have been conducted for SFR applications [1].
Metallic	Advanced metal	7	Hundreds of fuel rods have been irradiated in prototype SFR in the USA [1].
Other Ceramics	Zirconium hydride-based	6	Commonly used in TRIGA research reactor with concept development for LWRs [6].
	Carbide (U,Pu)C	7	It has been manufactured and irradiated in a prototype scale SFR, especially, in India [7].
	Nitride (UN)	7	It has been manufactured and irradiated in a prototype scale SFR in Russia [8].
	Coated particle-based, TRISO	7	Significant manufacturing and irradiation experience for prototype HTGRs [9].
	Silicide (U ₃ Si)	4	Westinghouse leads a LWR irradiation program [10].
Fluid-based	Molten salt	4	Experience of the use of U-based molten salts fuels in test reactors in the USA in the 1950s and 1960s [11].

*The TRL level is reduced from 10 to 9 as the highest TRL level is widely accepted to be 9.

However, the maturity of each innovative fuels cannot be separated from the nuclear technology, namely Gen-III and Gen-IV. Several international attempts have been conducted worldwide to increase the maturity of some innovative fuels depending on the nuclear technologies used.

Summary as presented in Table 3 is an attempt to collect the available innovative fuels, and class them based on the nuclear technologies and TRL. The UO₂-doped fuels, commonly used for LWRs, have high maturity, while some improved UO₂-doped fuels still have a really low maturity. In term of the high-density fuels (nitride, silicide, carbide, and metallic fuels) for LWRs, their maturity is characterized as low. In term of the Gen-IV technology, only MOX, UN, and advanced fuels for SFRs have a relatively high maturity (TRL). The GFR, MSR, (V)HTR and SCWR are unfortunately known to have a low maturity fuel [3] [12].

However, due to a continuous improvement and development, it is currently difficult to pinpoint the exact TRL maturity of each innovative fuels [3]. Furthermore, the progress of each development of each fuel is not the same. The latest ranking was provided by

ORIENT-NM identity card in 2022 [12]. By comparing those ranking, it is clear that there is some redundancy of some fuel development of specific technologies. It can be seen in the case of the high Pu-content and UN fuels where the ORIENT-NM identity card classified them as high TRL > 7 for the GFR, LFR and (V)HTR. Another case is for the UC where it is currently mentioned as TRL of 5 [12].

Table 3 summary of collected innovative fuels classed based on the nuclear technologies and their estimated TRL, summarised and modified from Shepherd, et al. [3] and [12].

	Estimated TRL							
	Gen III		Gen IV					
	LWR	HWR	SFR	GFR	LFR	MSR	HTR/ VHTR	SCWR
UO₂	9 ^a	9 ^a	-	-	-	-	7	3
High Gd₂O₃-doped UO₂	2	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
MOX (<12% Pu)	9 ^a	9 ^a	-	-	-	-	4	3
Advanced MOX	7 2 ^c	-	9	3 7 [§]	4 7 [§]	-	2 8 [§]	2
Cr₂O₃ and Al₂O₃-doped UO₂	9	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
Nb₂O₃-doped UO₂	7	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
UO₂ annular pellet	7 ^b	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Cr₂O₃ doped MOX	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Thorium-contained	5	8 ^d	4	1	2	4	6	2
UN	3	-	7	1 8 [§]	4 8 [§]	-	2 8 [§]	1 8 [§]
Advanced metal	4 7 [§]	-	7	1	4	-	-	1
U₂Si₃	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Coated particle	5	-	-	-	-	-	2 – 7 ^f	1
UC	2	-	7	3 5 [§]	2 5 [§]	-	6 ^e 5 [§]	1
MA	4	-	4	2	3	2	2	2
Zr hydride-based	5	-	-	2	-	-	-	1
Molten salt	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-

^aThe TRL level from is reduced from 10 to 9 as the highest TRL level is widely accepted to be 9.

^bTRL = 9 in VVER

^cHigh Pu content

^dOnce through the Th-recycle

^fAs UCO in coated particles

^eDepends on the kernel type

[§]From the ORIENT-NM identity card [12]

2.2 Fuel qualification approaches

2.2.1 Classical approach

The classical approach and rationale of fuel qualification process was documented in 2007 [13]. The TRL is used to define the maturity of nuclear fuels while qualification process is a set of phases followed to achieve those levels. Because a fuel program requires long-lead-time irradiation testing, the time span of 20 - 25 years is required to reach the high maturity for the deployment in the nuclear reactor.

This approach divides the TRL levels into several “Fuel Development Phases” (Table 4). Each phase has its specific objectives with phase 4 being the longest, and for up to ~8 years.

Table 4 Technical readiness level (TRL) in correlation to the fuel development phases [14].

TRL	Fuel Development-Specific Definition	Fuel Dev. Phase	Time
1	Phase 1. Fuel candidate selection Identify fuel types and concepts with potential for meeting mission requirements.	1	Year 0 - 2
2			
3	Phase 2. Concept definition and feasibility Establish a reference fuel concept and design.	2	Year 2 - 10
4			
5	Phase 3. Fuel design improvement and evaluation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimize the reference fuel design for performance, safety, and economics. Prepare a fuel specification and a licensing safety case for a reactor core of the reference fuel. Establish a predictive fuel performance code (or codes). 	3	Year 7 - 14
6			
7	Phase 4. Fuel qualification and demonstration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate engineering-scale or full-scale fuel production in conformance with the fuel specification (i.e., qualify the fabrication process). Qualify production-line fuel by demonstrating fuel performance to be within the bounds of the licensing safety case. Confirm acceptable fuel behaviour under design-basis accident conditions anticipated for a licensable reactor system. Demonstrate the safety and reliability of a core or partial core of reference fuel, accumulating reactor performance data and operating experience. Validate the predictive fuel performance code or codes. 	4	Year 15 - 23
8			

2.2.2 Accelerated approach

Looking at the timeline taken to follow the classical fuel qualification approach, it becomes clear that a change in a paradigm is needed. There is a need to combine worldwide effort to reduce the time to qualify nuclear fuels.

The US – NRC proposed an attempt to reduce the time span so called “Accelerated Fuel Qualification (AFQ)” (Table 5). The AFQ consists of three phases where phase 1 (basis irradiation effect and equilibrium thermodynamics) is carried on at the year 0 (zero) followed by phase 2 taking up to 4 years, and phase 3 taking up to 5 years, with the total time required to have a mature fuel of ~9 years [15] [16] [17] [18].

The timeline proposed is a promising timeline, at the same time, looking at the comparison between classical approach and AFQ, it is clear that the phase 1 of the AFQ is a crucial phase as it may take several years to be fulfilled.

The visual illustration of the AFQ can be seen in Figure 1 as directly taken from the publication written by Terrani et al., 2020 [16]. Here, it is clear that phase 1 is focusing on the collection and assessment of available data in the case of basis irradiation effect and equilibrium thermodynamics while phase 1 focuses on the combination of integral fuel performance analysis and separate effect. The PIRT method (explained in the next chapter) is one of the useful methods to be used in phase 1, and further phase 2 of the AFQ as it will identify several phenomena for fuel qualification and which phenomena requires more data and experiment.

Table 5 Comparison of the classical fuel development to the “Accelerated Fuel Qualification” approaches [19].

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
Fuel. Dev. Phase 1	█	█	█																				
Fuel. Dev. Phase 2			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Fuel. Dev. Phase 3								█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Fuel. Dev. Phase 4																	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
AFQ Phase 1	█																						
<i>Basis irradiation effect</i>	█																						
<i>Equilibrium Thermodynamics</i>	█																						
AFQ Phase 2		█	█	█	█																		
<i>Integral Fuel Performance Analysis</i>		█	█	█	█																		
<i>Separate Effects Testing</i>		█	█	█	█																		
AFQ Phase 3						█	█	█	█	█													
<i>Integral Fuel Fabrication</i>						█	█	█	█	█													
<i>Integral Fuel Irradiation and Transient Testing</i>						█	█	█	█	█													
<i>Licensing Basis</i>						█	█	█	█	█													

Figure 1 Visual workflow of the Accelerated Fuel Qualification (AFQ) process taken from Terrani, et al., 2020 [16].

The effort to introduce an accelerated fuel qualification is earlier adopted by European community [20]. The idea is that the principle of an optimized validation and qualification process will lead to increased efficiency, thus, minimizing lost time. Table 6 is summarized from the document prepared by NEA in 2019 based on the TRL evaluation instead of time (years).

The TRLs 1 – 6 are combined into a specific “Material development and Scaling’ with a high focus on the predictive modelling or design envelope or fundamental properties on the normal condition as well as off-normal, transient and DBA. The steady state irradiation in the power plant and integral test in research reactor further cover TRL 7 – 8.

By looking at the two approaches proposed by US-NRC and European communities, the modelling and database utilization are fundamental. The PIRT approach can be again utilised to perform these specific tasks.

Table 6 Accelerated Fuel Qualification approach proposed by NEA, summarised from NEA – 2019 [20].

TRL	AFQ by OECD - NEA General description [20]	AFQ by OECD - NEA Detail description
1	Material development and scaling	Predictive modelling/ Design envelope/ Fundamental properties <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Separate effect in-pile & integral irradiation (normal condition). • Separate effect in-pile & integral irradiation (transient & DBA). • Analytical out-of-pile testing (normal & off-normal)
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Steady state irradiation of rod/ assembly in power plant. • Integral test in research reactor. 	
8		

Another approach was proposed, and a summary was written by Bertolus, et al., (2024) (within CONNECT NM project) focusing on the division between modelling and experimental. The proposal does not necessarily define any specific timeline [21];

- **Acceleration Qualification of Fuel Performance Code**

It focuses on the design & control of physics-based FPC leveraging separate-effect validation, combination of lower-length scale analyses and database and advanced modelling techniques.

- **Acceleration Qualification of property determination**

It focuses on the experiment-oriented modelling and modelling-oriented experiment, the use of ion or neutron irradiation, complementary multiscale modelling and determination of elementary mechanism governing the behaviour from the calculations and interpretation of experiment.

This approach clearly supports the acceleration approach proposes by both US – NRC and European communities as it is aligned with the need to focus on the modelling.

2.2.3 Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) Method

The “Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT)” is generally used as an approach to identify and rank certain phenomena as part of safety assessments. [22] [23] [24] [25] [26] [27]. It was introduced as early as the eighties for thermal-hydraulic phenomena during a PWR large-break LOCA [22]. The method has been then intensively used. Hence, several publications and reports are publicly available. This document, unfortunately, cannot listed all the publications and only several of them will be mentioned here.

The PIRT method requires several analysis steps as presented in Figure 2. An example of an extensive study of PIRT in “TRISO-Coated Particle Fuel Phenomenon Identification and Ranking Tables (PIRTs) for Fission Product Transport Due to Manufacturing, Operations, and Accidents” was written by Morris, et al., and published in 2004 [25]. This PIRT identified six phenomena, namely (1) manufacturing, (2) operations, (3) depressurized Heat up Accident, (4) Reactivity Accident, (5) Depressurization Accident with water Ingress, and (6) Depressurization Accident with air ingress and underlying features / mechanisms were ranked

After defining all the required information from step 1 to step 6, it is equally important to define the ranking. Generally, the rank can be defined based on the “Importance Level (or Ratio),” IL, and “Knowledge Level (or Ratio),” KL, which can be separated between the availability of the data and the availability of the model. In some case, another ranking such as “Applicability Level (or Ratio)” can be added [23] [24] [26]. The details of the ranking can be seen in Table 7.

Figure 2 Illustration of the PIRT flow chart [24].

Table 7 Three-level scale used for the “Importance Level” and “Knowledge Level” ranking.

Importance Level (IL)		
Rank	Definition	Implication
High (H)	The phenomenon has a dominant impact on any of the evaluation criteria	The phenomenon should be explicitly considered in experimental programs and modelled with high accuracy in computational tools
Medium (M)	The phenomenon has only a moderate impact on the evaluation criteria	Experimental studies and analytical modelling are required, but the scope and accuracy may be compromised
Low (L)	The phenomenon has small or no impact on the evaluation criteria	The phenomenon should be exhibited experimentally mentally and considered in computational tools. However, almost any model will be sufficient
$IL = \frac{1.0N_H + 0.5N_M + 0.0N_L}{N_H + N_M + N_L}$; with N_H , N_M and N_L are refer to the numbers of “High,” “Medium” and “Low” importance votes, respectively		
Knowledge Level (KL)		
Rank	Definition	Implication
Adequate (A)	The phenomenon is well understood. Data obtained for the specific problem are available in sufficient range, quantity, and quality.	Models that are validated for application to the specific problem are available.
Some (S)	Data obtained for the specific problem are available, but not in	The phenomenon can be app-approximately modelled, e.g., by

	sufficient range quantity or quality. Alternatively, data pertinent to other conditions exist and can be extrapolated the specific problem.	lower order models or models for and similar phenomena that can be extrapolated to the specific problem,
None (N)	No relevant data exist, and the phenomenon is poorly known.	No validated models exist

$$KL = \frac{1.0N_H + 0.5N_M + 0.0N_L}{N_H + N_M + N_L}$$

; with N_H , N_M and N_L are refer to the numbers of "High," "Medium" and "Low" importance votes, respectively

The correlation between the IL and KL can be then made and plotted using colour code (see Figure 3 as an example). The example is taken from "PIRT of R&D Priorities for Loss-of-Cooling and Loss-of-Coolant Accidents in Spent Nuclear Fuel Pools" [28]. The average Knowledge Level was calculated from the KL^D (data) and KL^M (model) for each specific phenomena as labelled with coded number. By having the color-coded results one can decide which phenomena or aspect needs to be developed and improved, or vice versa. The colour coding is not intended to categorise the phenomena, but merely to help the reader to identify at a glance the most interesting phenomena with regard to importance or lack of knowledge.

Figure 3 An example of graphical presentation of PIRT - R&D Priorities for Loss-of-Cooling and Loss-of-Coolant Accidents in Spent Nuclear Fuel Pools taken from OECD report, 2018 [26].

In general, the PIRT is used to assess the complete scenarios for the fuel qualification of a specific technology. However, a small PIRT assessment can be performed, such as to assess the fuel material properties for manufacturing and irradiation purposes. One of the examples is the use of PIRT to identify phenomena that limit the fuel performance of uranium-zirconium fuel to identify potential knowledge gaps, which was published by Williams, et al., in 2020 [28].

In this study fuel swelling and constituent redistribution were identified and further analysed.

This PIRT was initiated by identifying and exploring the main phenomena affecting the bulk fuel behaviours in correlation to the cladding materials within the U-Zr system (Figure 4). The further step was to define variables used to perform the PIRT in which a general scoring system as seen Table 7 was used and slightly modified showing that the a high weighting factor illustrates a potential knowledge gap, or an area where more investigation may be required [28]. There are up to eighteen variables from five families of source variables in which each of them was scored in correlation to either U-Zr fuel swelling and U-Zr fuel constituent redistribution.

Figure 4 Summary of the correlation between fuel and cladding within fuel metallic system illustrating the fuel performance model, taken from Williams, et al. (2020) [28].

Figure 5 Score representation from the PIRT with relative weighting factors resulting from equation: $IR \cdot (100 - KR) / 100$, taken from Williams, et al. (2020) [28].

3. Relevant properties of nuclear fuels

In order to fulfil the TRL of the fuel qualification, there are several precedent steps need to be taken into accounts, such as fuel fabrication, pre-irradiation examination of the fabricated fuels and post irradiation examination of the fuels irradiated under specific conditions (either via separate effect or integral irradiation) [16].

These precedent steps focus on the fuel properties investigation. A general required fuel properties summarized from several sources is presented in Figure 6 with each details properties presented in Table 8. These properties are needed to be used as inputs for FPC, as can be seen in the flowchart presented in (Figure 4), and can be measured using several available techniques as presented in Table 9. However, the technique is not limited to those mentioned in this report. Several other techniques can be developed for certain purposes while at the same time the technique can be exchangeable. Moreover, depending on the fuels, the characterisation technique can be different.

The required properties of the nuclear fuels presented here is a general and is simply a

proposal. Each fuel may have less requirements or even more. It additionally depends on the reactor technology used.

Figure 6 Typical properties used to characterised innovative fuels, summarised from varied documents [14] [19] [21].

Table 8 Physical, thermophysical and mechanical properties of nuclear fuels.

Physical properties	Thermophysical properties	Mechanical properties
Melting point (solid & aq.)	Thermal conductivity	Young's modulus
Emissivity	Specific heat (solidus & aq.)	Poisson's ratio
Theoretical density	Enthalpy	Yield stress
Diffusion/ migration of fission gas	Thermal expansion (solid & aq.)	Ultimate stress
Diffusion/ migration of pores		Creep
Diffusion/ migration of atom		
Other properties: Lattice parameter, oxygen potential, grain properties (size, growth, etc.)		

Table 9 Several available techniques used to measure the properties of nuclear fuels.

Nuclear fuel properties	Possible measurement techniques
Theoretical via volumetric (geometric) or physical density	Pycnometer, immersion measurement, etc.
Thermal conductivity	Laser Flash Analysis, Knudsen measurement, etc.
Fission gas release	Gas-mass spectroscopy, ICP-MS, etc.
Specific heat	Differential Scanning Calorimetry, etc.
Young's modulus	Hardness test, etc.
Melting point	Laser melting measurement, etc.
Burn-up	ICP-MS, Gamma spectroscopy, etc.
Diffusion/ migration of pores	Optical microscope, SEM, etc.
Diffusion/ migration of atom	SEM – EDS, SEM – WDS, EPMA, XRF, XAS, etc.
Grain properties	SEM – EBSD, XRD, etc.
Visual analysis	Neutron radiography, X-ray tomography, etc.
Defect analysis	Positron Annihilation technique, TEM, etc.
Other possible techniques	Raman spectroscopy, AFM, Thermal Desorption Spectroscopy, Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS), Neutron Diffraction, etc.

3.1 General HCL capabilities

3.1.1 Pre - Irradiation Examination

One of the most important requirements to perform fuel fabrication and pre-irradiation examination is the availability of glove box or necessary labs. OFFERR project funded by EURATOM recently published an "OFFERR - European User Facility Network Catalogue of Facilities," in February 2025 summarizing the availability of laboratory in Europe to perform nuclear related analysis, including nuclear fuel fabrication and, pre- and post-irradiation examination [29].

Due to the intensive amount of the pre-IE needed to qualify nuclear fuels, the collaborations with other institutes are imminent.

3.1.2 PIE

The post irradiation examination is not less critical than the pre-IE. However, the PIEs are deemed to be more difficult due to its nature as hot cell labs. are required to handle irradiated fuels. Table 10 summarized the available HCL to perform PIE of irradiated materials.

Table 10 A general summary of the availability of HCL [29].

No.	Institute	Country	Overview
1.	CEA	France	Various labs around France to handle <i>irradiated fuels</i> .
2.	CV Rez.	Czech Republic	It consists of ten hot cells and one semi-hot cell. Available equipment includes cutting, welding, machining, equipment for performing mechanical tests (deformation tests, fatigue, creep, etc.), and equipment for studying the microstructure of the material (measurement of microhardness and nano hardness of the samples, evaluation of the microstructure using a scanning electron microscope). <i>No specific capability to work with irradiated fuel is mentioned.</i>
3.	HZDR	Germany	The hot cell platform is devoted to the mechanical characterisation of structural material for nuclear application such as reactor pressure vessel steels, martensitic/ferritic Cr-steels, or Fe-Cr ODS alloys. Available equipment includes quasi-static fracture toughness properties from SE(B) and C(T) specimens, dynamic toughness properties from instrumented impact testing, small punch tests, preparation and light microscopy for metallographic inspections, SEM analyses, and electrical discharging machine (EDM). <i>No specific capability to work with irradiated fuel is mentioned.</i>
4.	JRC	Europe	JRC owns several HCL that can be used to perform PIEs of <i>irradiated fuels</i> . It includes NDT, puncturing, X-ray radiography & diffraction, SEM, TEM, EPMA, SIMS, ICP-MS, gamma scanning and some tools to perform pyro reprocessing under pure Ar atmosphere equipped with electro refiner, molten salt, molten metal extractors, chlorination device [30]
5.	NRG PALLAS	Netherlands	The capabilities range from pre- to post irradiation examination, such as mechanical testing (fracture toughness testing, tensile, SPT, curve SPT, bending, compression, tube ring tensile), physical tests (thermal conductivity – LFA, thermal expansion dilatometry, sample mass, geometry, density, electrical resistivity) and microstructural (optical microscopy, SEM - EDS, WDS, EBSD, TEM, XRT). <i>The hotcell labs. are able to handle irradiated fuels.</i>
6.	Studsvik	Sweden	The hot cell laboratory is available for studies of <i>spent nuclear fuel and irradiated materials</i> . Available equipment includes visual inspection, dimension measurements, eddy current measurements, fission gas and inner pressure measurements, microstructural studies, refabrication of test rods for in or out of pile testing, intermediate and final storage simulations, transient simulations. The mechanical tests range from tensile testing, RIA simulations, creep and HRX testing, PCI simulation and crack initiation to propagation testing
7.	PSI	Switzerland	The PSI Hotlab is equipped with instrumentation for the manipulation, characterization and analysis of radioactive materials, such as hot cell line for sample preparation, material testing and dismantling of large components from the nuclear fuel cycle or accelerator systems,

			microstructure analysis (optical and electron microscopy), and Gamma, X-ray and Mass spectrometric techniques for the elemental and isotopic analysis of gaseous, liquid and solid samples incl. surface analytical techniques. <i>The hotcell labs. are not specifically able to handle irradiated fuels.</i>
8.	SCK.CEN	Belgium	SCK.CEN owns the Laboratory for high and medium activity (LHMA). It consists of a number of facilities for handling highly radioactive and/or toxic materials. The labs are equipped with robotic arms, glove boxes and hot cells including equipment for testing materials and preparing, conditioning, and storing samples. The hot cell laboratory is available for studies of <i>spent nuclear fuel and irradiated materials.</i>
9.	VTT	Finland	Available equipment includes electric-discharge machining, electron-beam welding, fracture characterization by macroscopy and optical dimensioning. <i>No specific capability to work with irradiated fuel is mentioned.</i>

3.2 Practical examples

3.2.1 MOX fuel

Several attempts in Europe involving several European Research Projects have been conducted to study and investigate the MOX fuel qualification for Gen-IV – Fast Reactors [21] [31] [32]. The objective is to feed the FPC with important missing input to complete the models. Table 11 summarised the required properties that was summarised based on the needs for MOX for the fast reactor and the range of interests, such as temperature Pu/U ratio, O/M ratio, fraction of the porosity, grain size, stress and burn-up [21] [32]. The table, however, is not completed with the information whether those required properties within the range of interest are currently available or not. The Table 11 can be used for the underlying material properties and their evolution during analysis of failure modes and further PIRT to identify the gaps in certain regimes of the material property database. Additionally, one needs to understand that the range of interest depends on the requirement of the technology used.

The PIRT approach can be used to assess the Knowledge Level (KL) in comparison to the Importance Level (IL) presented in Table 11. The KL can be divided into two, namely the knowledge availability of model and of the experimental data.

Table 11 Summary of the properties for MOX – FR and the range of interest.

	Parameters of influence/ (Range of interest)						
	Temp. (293K – BP)	Pu/U ratio (15-35%)	O/M ratio (1.94-2.00)	Porosity (0–40%)	Grain size (4–30 μm)	Stress (1–100 MPa)	BU (0–125 GWd/t)
Lattice parameter	x	x	x				x
Thermal conductivity	x	x	x	x			x
Melting point		x	x				x
Specific heat	x	x	x				x
Enthalpy of fusion		x	x				x
Emissivity	x	x	x				x
Theoretical density	x	x	x				
Thermal expansion	x	x	x				x
Young's modulus	x	x	x	x			
Poisson's ratio	x	x	x	x			
Yield stress	x	x	x	x			
Ultimate stress	x	x	x	x			
Thermal creep	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Diffusion/ migration of fission gas	x	x	x				
Diffusion/ migration of fission pores	x	x	x				
Diffusion/ migration of fission Oxygen	x	x	x				
Diffusion/ migration of fission U, Pu	x	x	x				
Oxygen potential	x	x	x				x
Grain growth	x			x	x		

3.2.2 U-Zr (metallic) fuel

A clear example to study fuel as part of the fuel qualification was earlier presented using PIRT for U-Zr (metallic) fuel (Figure 4 and Figure 5). The PIRT focuses on the fuel swelling and fuel constituent redistribution [28]. The committee for PIRT study consists of several experts, fourteen experts in this example, to investigate phenomena in U-Zr fuels subjected to neutron irradiation, namely fuel swelling, fuel constituent redistribution, fuel-cladding chemical interaction (FCCI), and fuel-cladding mechanical interaction (FCMI) (Figure 4) [28].

The committee further decided to focus the PIRT on only two main phenomena (fuel swelling and fuel constituent redistribution) and the source variables used were identified to be ranked based on the impact ratio (IR) and knowledge ration (KR) (Figure 5).

This is one of the clear of the practical use of the PIRT. It is generally applicable to study other fuel phenomena for each specific fuel and technologies. Based on the PIRT output, once can conclude and design better experiments (either data modelling or practical experiments) to complete the dataset in order to better understand the defined phenomena. This will further be used as a path for fuel qualification process.

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